
ECONOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF RICE IMPORT DEMAND IN NIGERIA (1970 – 2008): AN APPLICATION OF AUTOREGRESSIVE DISTRIBUTED LAGS (ARDL) MODELLING APPROACH TO COINTEGRATION.

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the economic factors which influence the rice import demand in Nigeria between 1970 and 2008. The quantity of rice imports was considered as a function of factors such as the amount of the lagged import, exchange rate, external reserves, structural adjustment programme (SAP), per capita income and import price of rice. However, quantitative estimates, based on cointegration and error correction specification using the Bound's testing approach, indicate that per capita income is the most important determinant of rice import in Nigeria. The results further alludes that, the error correction mechanism (ECM) indicated a feedback of about 16.9 % of the previous year's disequilibrium from long-run wheat import. It is concluded that for the Nigerian government to reduce importation of rice in the face of increasing rice demand without exacerbating food security problem, then Nigeria should as a matter of urgency put in place policy measures that will significantly improve local rice production and processing.

KEYWORDS: Rice, demand, import, SAP, ARDL, error correction mechanism, co-integration.

INTRODUCTION

The domestic economy of Nigeria is dominated by Agriculture, which accounts for about 40% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and two-third of the labour force. Agriculture supplies food, raw material and generates house hold income for the majority of the people. The external sector is dominated by petroleum, which generates about 95% of Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings while agriculture contributes less than 5%. Trade imports are dominated by capital foods, raw materials and food.

Nigeria is the largest rice producing country in the West African region. Rice production rose gradually over the years with area expansion to surpass major rice producing countries like Cote d'Ivoire and Sierra Leone. The principal factors driving increased rice production in Nigeria is population growth and urbanisation. In 2002, Nigeria accounted for nearly 44 % of the total rice output and 57 % of the total rice producing area in West Africa (WARDA 1996). Rice yields are however low even by West African standards. Paradoxically Nigeria is also the largest importer of rice in the world. The annual demand for rice in the country is estimated at 5 million tons, while production level is 3 million tons of milled rice resulting in a deficit of 2 million tons. Over the years the country had resorted to imports to bridge this deficit. For instance in 1999, the value of rice imports was US\$259 million and this increased to US\$655 million in 2001 and US\$756 in 2002. Between 1990 and 2002, Nigeria imported 5,132,616 tons of rice valued at US\$1,883,553 million. In 2002 alone, the country imported 1.882 million tons of rice (FAO 2002). Because rice has become a strategic commodity in the Nigerian economy, it is important to examine the factors determining the demand for rice in Nigeria with a view to improve production and as much as possible reduce rice importation in Nigeria without causing food crisis in the long-run.

Conceptual Framework and Theoretical issues

As in Binuomote *et al* (2010), the import demand theory alluded to in this study has a micro foundation. It is based on consumer theory of demand, which states that the aim of the consumer is to minimize satisfaction and so income is

allocated among competing goods to obtain maximum satisfaction. This argument is extended to the demand for imports—that is, the demand for imports by a consumer is influenced by income, import prices themselves, and prices of other commodities. The sum total of individual demand for imports constitutes the aggregate imports for the economy (Lerner and Stern, 1970). According to Sodersten and Reed (1994), part of consumers' aggregate demand is assumed to be expressed as an increasing function of national income. That is $M = f(Y)$ with $\delta m/\delta y > 0$, where M is imports and Y is national income. Since aggregate demand consists of demand for domestically produced goods (Q_d) and for imports, it follows that we may write the marginal propensity to consume (MPC) as the sum of the MPC of domestically produced goods ($Q_d = \delta Q_d/\delta y$) and the MPC of imports ($M = \delta m/\delta y$). Assuming that imports are a linear function of national income, as income increases, imports also increase. The marginal propensity to import measures how much of an increase in national income is spent on imports.

However, studies that are recent exist in Nigeria for aggregate import demand and food import demand. A more recent study is that of Nkang *et al* (2006) which examined the rice production, import and food security in Nigeria applying cointegration and error correction model spanning from 1970 to 2002. The model specification was based on the OLS multiple regression, while the estimate procedure made use of cointegration and error correction model with empirical evidence that short-run changes in domestic rice production, level of external reserves and total imports value remarkably shaped rice import behaviour in Nigeria during the period under investigation. In his own study also, Egwakhide (1999) analyzed the determinants of aggregate imports in Nigeria using co-integration and error correction specification and came out with satisfactory results. Quantitative evidence of the study indicated that short-run changes in the availability of foreign exchange earnings, relative prices and real output significantly explain the growth of total imports during the period under investigation. Particularly striking was the short-run impact of foreign exchange availability, which is tied to the long-run effect via a feed back mechanism. He concluded that although all the earlier mentioned variables played a role in shaping import behaviour, the effect of foreign exchange availability is particularly remarkable. Another recent study is that of Udoh *et al* (2001) which made use of a modification of the traditional import demand model and the Hemphill model (Hemphill, 1974) to estimate the demand for the food commodities in Nigeria. The model was estimated via the OLS method using a Cobb-Douglas function. The results reveal that all the factors considered individually and collectively affect the quantities of the food import demand. However, Komolafe (1994) focused on modelling import demand under quantitative trade restrictions using co-integration theory as estimation techniques. The study investigated an outstanding issue concerning the orthodox model of import demand which incorporates a domestic economic activity and relative price. The result in general, reveal the adjustment responsiveness of the import sector which pass across a message that imports have not been liberalized in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Following the theory of demand, it is hypothesised in this study that the import demand for rice is a function of the relative price of rice, external reserve – since the ability of a nation to import will be a function of her available external reserve, per- capita income, price and real exchange rate. Empirically, the model is stated as:

$$LM = \alpha + \delta_1 LEX_t + \delta_2 LER_t + \delta_3 LP_{Rt} + \delta_4 LY_t + \delta_5 SAP + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots (1)$$

where LM is the quantity of rice imported into Nigeria, LEX is the real exchange rate, LER is Nigeria's external reserve while the import price of rice is given as LP_R

per- capita income and structural adjustment programme are represented by LY , and SAP

respectively. All the variables are expressed in the natural logarithmic form. The dummy variable SAP is included in this study to examine the effect of market reforms policies on rice import in Nigeria. It is expected that market reform will increase domestic rice production and consequently lower the import. Theoretically, it is expected that

$$\delta_1 \leq 0, \delta_2 \geq 0, \delta_3 \leq 0, \delta_4 \geq 0, \text{ and } \delta_5 \leq 0.$$

ARDL Model Specification

As obtained in Fosu and Magnus (2008), in order to empirically analyse the long-run relationships and dynamic interactions among the variables of interest, the model has been estimated by using the Bounds testing (or autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL)) cointegration procedure, developed by Pesaran *et al* (2001). The procedure is adopted for the following three reasons. Firstly, the bounds test procedure is simple. As opposed to other multivariate cointegration techniques such as Johansen and Juselius (1990), it allows the cointegration relationship to be estimated by OLS once the lag order of the model is identified. Secondly, the Bounds testing procedure does not require the pre-testing of the variables included in the model for unit roots unlike other techniques such as the Johansen approach. It is applicable irrespective of whether the regressors in the model are purely I (0) purely I (1) or mutually cointegrated. Thirdly, the test is relatively more efficient in small or finite sample data sizes as is the case in this study. The procedure will however crash in the presence of I(2) series. Following Pesaran *et al* (2001), we apply the bounds test procedure by modelling the long-run equation (6) as a general vector autoregressive (VAR) model of order p , in

$$z_t = c_o + \beta t + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i z_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t, \quad t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, T \quad \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

with c_o representing a $(k+1)$ -vector of intercepts (drift) and β denoting a $(k+1)$ -vector of trend coefficients. Pesaran *et al* (2001) further derived the following vector equilibrium correction model (VECM) corresponding to (6)

$$\Delta z_t = c_0 + \beta t + \pi z_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \Gamma_i \Delta z_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t, \quad t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, T \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where the $(k+1) \times (k+1)$ matrices $\Pi = I_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \psi_i$ and $\Gamma_i = -\Pi = \sum_{j=i+1}^p \psi_j, i = 1, 2, \dots, p-1$

contain the long-run multipliers and short-run dynamic coefficients of the VECM. Z_t is the vector of variables y_t and x_t respectively. y_t is an I(1) dependent variable defined as LM_t and

$X_t = (LY, LEX, LER, LP_R, SAP)$ is a vector matrix of ‘forcing’ I(0) and I(1) regressors as already defined with a multivariate identically and independently distributed (*i.i.d*) zero mean error vector $\varepsilon_t = (\varepsilon_{1t}, \varepsilon_{2t})$ and a homoskedastic process. Further assuming that a unique long-run relationship exists among the variables, the conditional VECM can now becomes:

$$\Delta y_t = C_{yo} \beta_t + \delta_{yy} y_{t-1} + \delta_{xx} x_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \lambda_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} \xi_i \Delta x_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{yt}, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

On the basis of equation (4) above, the conditional VECM of interest can now be specified as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta LM = & \alpha + \delta_1 LM_{t-1} + \delta_2 LEX_{t-1} + \delta_3 LER_{t-1} + \delta_4 LP_{Rt-1} + \delta_5 LY_{t-1} + \\ & \sum_{h=1}^p \eta \Delta LM_{t-h} + \sum_{i=1}^q \phi \Delta LEX_{t-d} + \sum_{j=1}^q w \Delta LER_{t-z} + \sum_{k=1}^q \phi \Delta LP_{Rt-w} + \sum_{l=1}^q \ell \Delta LY_{t-g} + \pi SAP \end{aligned} \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

where δ are the long run multipliers, c_0 is the drift and ε_t are white noise errors. Where all variables are previously defined.

There are 3 steps in testing the co integration relationship between rice import demand and its explanatory variables. First, we estimated equation above by ordinary least square (OLS) technique. The presence of cointegration can be traced by conducting an F-test for the joint significance of the coefficients of the lagged levels of the variables. That is, the null hypothesis

$H_0 : \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = \delta_4 = \delta_5 = 0$ against the alternative.
 $H_a : \delta_1$ or δ_2 or δ_3 or δ_4 or $\delta_5 \neq 0$.

We denote the test which normalize on M by $M = F_M(Y, EX, ER, P_R, SAP)$. Two asymptotic critical values bounds provide a test for cointegration when the independent variables are I(d) (where $0 \leq d \leq 1$): a lower value assuming the regressors are I(0) and an upper value assuming purely I(1) regressors. If the computed F- statistic is less than lower bound critical value, then we do not reject the null hypothesis of no co integration. Conversely, if the computed F- statistic is greater than upper bound critical value, then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there exists steady state equilibrium between the variables under study. However, if the computed F - value falls within lower and upper bound critical values, then the result is in conclusive. The appropriate critical values for the F-tests are obtained. Critical values for the I(0) series are referred to as the upper bound critical values while the critical values for the I(1) series are referred to as lower bound critical values.

For the second step, once the cointegration has been established consequent upon which a unique long run relationship exists among variables of interest, we specify a conditional ARDL (P, q₁, q₂, q₃, q₄, q₅, q₆) long run model for LM as

$$LM = c + \sum_{h=1}^p \delta_1 LM_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^q \delta_2 LEX_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \delta_3 LER_{t-1} + \sum_{k=0}^q \delta_4 LP_{R,t-1} + \sum_{l=0}^q \delta_5 LY_{t-1} + \pi SAP \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

The lags length in the ARDL model is selected based on Schwarz Bayesian criterion (SBC). For rice, a maximum of 2 lags was selected.

In the final step, we obtain the short-run dynamic elasticities by estimating an error correction model associated with the long run estimates. This is specified as follows:

$$\Delta LM = C_0 + \sum_{h=1}^p \eta \Delta LM_{t-n} + \sum_{i=1}^q \phi \Delta LEX_{t-d} + \sum_{j=1}^q \omega \Delta LER_{t-z} + \sum_{k=1}^q \varphi \Delta LP_{R,t-w} + \sum_{l=1}^q \ell \Delta LY_{t-g} + \pi SAP + \lambda ECM_{t-1} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

The symbols $\eta, \phi, \omega, \varphi$, and ℓ are the short-run dynamic elasticities of the model's convergence to long-run equilibrium and λ is the speed of adjustment. Δ represents the first difference operator and ECM_{t-1} is the one period lagged error correction term. The coefficient measures the speed of adjustment to obtain equilibrium in the event of shocks to the system. General – to – specific modeling technique of Hendry and Erricson (1991) is followed in selecting the preferred ECM. This procedure first estimate the ECM with different lag lengths for the difference terms and, then, simplify the representation by eliminating the lags with insignificant parameters. A correctly indicated ECM model has to pass a series of diagnosed tests. These include the Autoregressive LM (Lagrange multiplier) test and/or Durbin-Watson test for serial correlation in the residual, the Autoregressive LM test for normality distribution of the residuals in a regression model, the ARCH and the White test for heteroscedasticity in errors. These tests were conducted to ensure reliability of results.

Data Source

The data for this study are time series data at macro level spanning from 1970-2008. All the data were largely from Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) statistical data base, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin. Data on exchange rate were sourced from the PennWorld Data Table of the University of Pennsylvania. The data include quantity of imported rice in Nigeria, real exchange rate, import price, per- capita income of Nigeria and external reserve

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ARDL bounds test for co integration analysis for equation

Applying the steps, enumerated above, OLS regression is estimated for the first differences part of equation (1) and then test for the joint significance of the parameters of the lagged level variables when added to the first regression. The computed F-statistics from the Pesaran test is reported in table 1, according to the computed F-statistics, we can reject the null hypothesis of the no cointegration at 5% significance level for rice import demand. The computed F-statistics $M = F_M(M/Y, EX, ER, P_R, SAP) = 4.9902$ which is higher than the upper bound critical value of 4.329 at the 5% significance level. This indicates that the alternative hypothesis of the existence of a unique cointegration

relationship between rice import demand and its determinants can be accepted for Nigeria in this case. In other words, it has been proved that rice import demand, Per- capita income (*LY*), exchange rate (*EX*), external reserves (*LER*) and Structural adjustment programme (*SAP*), import prices of rice (*LP*), are bound together in the long -run (cointegrated) when rice import demand is made the dependent variable. The results of the solved static long- run equation for rice import demand in Nigeria as well as its short- run equation are given in the tables 2 below.

Table 1: ARDL bounds test for co integration analysis for equation

Critical values (F-Statistics) for the bounds test (Intercept and trend)						
1% level		5% level			10% level	
K	I (0)	I (1)	I (0)	I (1)	I (0)	I (1)
5	4.011	5.331	3.189	4.329	2.782	3.827
$F_M (M / Y, EX, ER, P, SAP)$					Computed F. Statistics = 4.990 **	

Source: Data analysis, 2011

Notes – Critical values are extracted from Pesaran *et al* (2001)

Critical values for bounds test: case III. K is the number of regressors.

Static long – run and Short -run Error Correction Results and Diagnostics.

The static long run result for rice import demand in Nigeria shows that the long- run elasticity for Per capita income (*LY*) is 13.71 and it is significant at 5%. This indicates that the national income significantly influence rice import demand in the long- run. This is in line with a-priori expectation since it is expected that when a nation’s income increases, the nation has capacity to increase its import. In the short -run also, the coefficient of Per- capita income is 3.7145 which is also statistically significant.

The coefficient of real exchange rate (*LEX*) in the long run is -0.447 and in the short run is -0.041. Both are not significant statistically. The result however suggests that a unit increase in the real exchange in the long- run reduces rice import demand by about 0.45 units and in the short run by 0.041 units. This result is in line with the theoretical expectation. One major objectives of *SAP* is reduction in the nation’s imports as result devaluation of the Naira. However, the variable was not significant both at the long-run and short- run suggesting that exchange rate is not a significant determinant of rice import in Nigeria.

The coefficient of structural adjustment programme (*SAP*) is -3.419 and insignificant in the long- run. An adequate and proper implementation of *SAP* policy is suppose decrease the rice import in the long -run and as a result encourage local production of rice through liberalization of input and output market. The non- significance of the variable in the long-run however suggests that *SAP* does not affect rice import in Nigeria. Nigeria is net food importer and there has not been any time that local production has been able to meet up with local demand.

External reserve (*LER*) has a positive impact on rice import demand. The coefficient is 1.482 in the long-run and 0.167 in the short run. This indicates that a unit rise in external reserves of Nigeria will result in 1.482 unit increases in rice import demand in the long- run and 0.168 units in the short run. Availability of external reserve is expected to increases the nation’s power to import. It can however be seen from tables 2 and 3 below that external reserve did not affect rice import significantly both at long and short-run.

The coefficient for import price (*LP*) elasticity in the long- run is -1.327. This indicates that import price will be negatively related to rice import demand and it is in line with the theoretical expectation. A unit increase in the import prices will reduce rice import demand by about 1.33%. This is in line with the law of demand as it is expected that an increase in import prices will reduce demand for imports, as imported goods become relatively more expensive while demand for imported goods increase as domestic price increases.

Trend captures all factors inherent in time such as infrastructural developments, expenditure on agricultural research and extensions, applications of modern techniques, use of genetically modified seeds for cultivation. The coefficient of trend is -0.761, this has a negative effect and it is not statistically significant in rice import demand in Nigeria. It suggests that development of infrastructures and provision of adequate services through extension agents to rice producers in Nigeria is not yet sufficient to significantly increase rice production in Nigeria.

It is observed from the results in table 3 that the coefficient of error correction term (*ECM*) carries the expected negative sign and it is significant at 5%. The significance of the (*ECM*) supports cointegration and suggests the existence of long- run steady state equilibrium between rice import demand and other determining factors in the specified model. The coefficient of -0.169 indicates that the deviation of rice import from the long run equilibrium level is corrected by 16.9% in the current period. It also suggests that in Nigeria, an adjustment from the short- run to long-run equilibrium is very slow.

The R² value of 0.724 in table 3 shows the overall goodness of fit of the (*ECM*) is satisfactory. The Auto Regressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (ARCH) test for testing heteroscedasticity in the error process in the model has an F-statistic of 0.00057 which statistically insignificant. This suggests that there is no heteroscedasticity in the model. The Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test for higher order – serial correlation with an F-statistic of 0.712 could not reject the null of absence of serial correlation in the residuals. The Jacque – Bera χ^2 – statistic of 0.194 for the test of normality in the distribution in the error process shows that the error process is normally distributed. From the battery of diagnostic tests presented above, this study concludes that the model is well estimated and that the observed data fits the model specification adequately, thus the residuals are expected to be distributed as white noise and the coefficient valid for policy discussions.

Table 2: Static long- run and Short- run Error Correction Modelling of Rice Imports in Nigeria

ARDL (2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion Dependent variable is LM 37 observations were used for estimation (1970 – 2007)

Static Long – run equation	Parsimonious Short – run equation
Constant -190.3(1.793)	Constant -0.151 (-1.761)
<i>LY</i> 13.71(1.756)*	$\Delta LM(-2)$ 0.101 (0.729)
<i>LEX</i> -0.448(-0.888)	ΔLY 3.715 (4.022)***
<i>LER</i> 1.482(0.953)	$\Delta LEX(-1)$ -0.041 (-0.644)
<i>SAP</i> -3.419(-1.112)	$\Delta LER(-1)$ -0.154 (-1.357)
<i>LP</i> -1.327(-0.661)	ΔLP -0.078 (-0.449)
<i>Trend</i> -0.761(-1.230)	$\Delta LP(-1)$ -0.168 (-0.968)
	ΔSAP 0.336(0.831)
	<i>ECM</i> (-1) -0.169(-5.063)*
	R ² = 0.724
	AR LM F (2, 22) = 0.072 (0.9308)
	ARCH F(1, 22) = 0.001 (0.9811)
	Normality χ^2 = 0.194 (0.9075)
	Reset F = 0.490(0.492)

Source: Data analysis, 2011. NB: * Indicates significance at 10%, ** Indicates significance at 5 % *** Indicates significance at 1%
 $ECM = LM + 190.3 - 13.71LY + 0.448LEX - 1.482LER + 1.327LP + 3.419SAP + 0.761Trend$

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study uses the Bound's testing approach to cointegration and error correction modeling to examine the rice import demand in Nigeria. Time series data comprising Per capita income (LY), Exchange rate (LEX), External Reserves (LER), Import Price of rice (LP) Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) were used in examining the relationship between rice import demand and the aforementioned selected factors. The result of this research shows that per capita income of Nigeria is the most important determinant of rice import in Nigeria. It also shows that Exchange rate, relative prices, SAP and Trend have not significantly affected rice import demand in Nigeria. Nigeria, as this results show is highly dependent on rice import and all policies geared towards decreasing rice import have not significantly achieved its objectives in the long run.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION

There is need for the government to ensure the implementation of policies that will encourage local rice production in order to reduce import; by providing incentives, credit facilities, subsidies and favourable price policies. It is also important for the government of Nigeria to intensify the services of extension agents by providing them with current technological innovations and developments, improved rice varieties, and provision of infrastructural development which will significantly increase rice production in Nigeria.

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